

THE ROLE OF MOTIVATION IN LEARNING LANGUAGE

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Abstract: This thesis analyzes the role of motivation in students' language learning process and its impact on effectiveness. Both internal and external motivation play a significant role in language learning. Internal motivation is related to a student's personal interest and desire for self-development, while external motivation is driven by grades, exam results, or career opportunities. High motivation encourages students to practice regularly, making the learning process more effective. Therefore, enhancing motivation in the language learning process is of great importance.

Keywords: Intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, language, success, difficulty, goal, encouragement.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tezisdagi talabalarning til o'rganish jarayonida motivatsiyaning tutgan o'rni va uning samaradorlikka ta'siri tahlil qilinadi. Til o'rganishda ichki va tashqi motivatsiya muhim rol o'ynaydi. Ichki motivatsiya talabaning shaxsiy qiziqishi, o'zini rivojlantirish istagi bilan bog'liq bo'lsa, tashqi motivatsiya baholar, imtihon natijalari yoki kasbiy imkoniyatlar orqali rag'batlantiriladi. Yuqori motivatsiya talabani muntazam mashq qilishga undab, o'quv jarayonini samarali qiladi. Shu sababli, til o'rganish jarayonida motivatsiyani oshirish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Ichki motivatsiya, tashqi motivatsiya, til, muvaffaqiyat, qiyinchilik, maqsad, rag'batlantirish.

Аннотация: В данной работе анализируется роль мотивации в процессе изучения языка студентами и ее влияние на эффективность. Как внутренняя, так и внешняя мотивация играют значительную роль в изучении языка. Внутренняя мотивация связана с личным интересом студента и его стремлением к саморазвитию, в то время как внешняя мотивация обусловлена оценками, результатами экзаменов или карьерными возможностями. Высокая мотивация побуждает студентов к регулярной практике, делая процесс обучения более эффективным. Поэтому повышение мотивации в процессе изучения языка имеет большое значение.

Ключевые слова: внутренняя мотивация, внешняя мотивация, язык, успех, сложность, цель, поощрение.

Introduction. Nowadays, learning a language is one of the most important skills and motivation plays crucial role in this process, because it helps individuals overcome challenges in language learning. Motivation is a powerful internal force that encourages learners to achieve their goals and move forward with forgetting past failures and challenges. In this research, I want to discuss the problems and benefits of motivation in language learning. In recent years, most scientists explored researches, however some important aspects of motivation still unexplored and my main aim is identifying the role of motivation in successful language learning. The objectives of this research are:

- Analyzing types of motivation,

- Examining their impact on learners performance,
- Determining effective motivational factors.

Literature review. My research is conducted with Yang and Wu(2022) and Wu(2022) research that is particular important in this field. According to them, motivation plays a key role in learners ability to effectively use language in real communication situations.[Yang Wu,2022-Scopus]. Scientific sources define it differently. Some researchers consider intrinsic motivation as the main factor that influence success, while others think extrinsic motivation is more significant, such as career opportunities and academic goals.

Intrinsic motivation comes from inside the person and you do something because you enjoy from it and find it interesting. For example, Ali is a university student who started to learn English. He does not have any exam pressure or job requirement. He simply enjoy from watching English movies or English songs. At first it can be difficult, but he has intrinsic motivation, that is why he continues without concentrating his mistakes. That is because he learns English, as it helps him to learn other cultures and find new friends.

However, **extrinsic motivation** comes from outside rewards or pressure and you do it to get result or avoid something negative. For instance, Sara is also learning English, but her reason is different. She needs to take higher score from IELTS, because she applies for scholarship abroad. Her university also requires the certificate for graduation. When learning is difficult for her, she realizes that without that certificate, she fails and cannot achieve her goals. Sara's motivation is extrinsic because she wants scholarship and career opportunities. External goals and expectations drive her learning.

The results show that motivation significantly influences language learning outcomes. Motivated students practice regularly and use effective learning strategies with a help of it they achieve higher levels of proficiency like Ali and Sara. The obtained results confirm the findings of Yang and Wu who emphasize the importance of motivation in communication skills. At the same time, some unexpected factors were also identified, such as the role of external pressure. In Yang and Wu research, they consider intrinsic motivation is dominant, but I think that the combination of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation is more effective than having only one type.

Methods of increasing motivation:

Motivation can be improved through several strategies.

1. Creating supportive and engaging learning environment,
2. Maintaining focus and direction with a help of goal-setting,
3. Making learning more interactive with technologies such as mobile applications, online platforms and multimedia tools,
4. Rewarding themselves.

Conclusion. Motivation plays a crucial role in language learning. Both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation significantly influence success. Effective teaching strategies should use improve both types of motivation. This research helps to understand motivational factors and highlight the importance of integrating motivational strategies in education.

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